

THE EFFECTS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON UNIVERSITY ACTIVITY

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Abstract

Purpose – In any field of activity, certain major changes cause disturbances in the smooth running of activities. The way we manage our work and adapt to change makes us stronger and helps us progress. The pandemic has been a real challenge for the students and the teachers. Education must be able to adapt to any crisis situation. The aim of this study is to find solutions that can be adopted in case a similar pandemic will have place in the future.

Methodology/approach - The study consisted in the realization of a questionnaire, distributed to the students from all the years of study in university, from the specialization Constructions Engineering and Management (IMC) of the Faculty of Civil Engineering from Cluj-Napoca. We proposed this study because we are directly interested by the opinion of our students and we wanted to offer them the opportunity to express themselves directly and freely on issues related to the university environment.

Findings – The Covid-19 pandemic was one of the biggest challenges faced by humanity in recent years. The pandemic has affected the countries' economy and it has had a major impact on the socio-emotional side, through the isolation restrictions imposed. In any field of activity the most important resource is the human one, which must be protected. The effects of the pandemic were also felt in education. School is both a place of study and a place where social and emotional skills interact and develop.

Research limitations/implications – The paper presents the results of a research, which aimed to determine the problems faced by students during the pandemic. Through the proposed analysis we wanted to identify the problems that affected and influenced the academic and social life of the students, due to the lack of physical interaction over a long period of time.

Practical implications – Achieving the desired results and increasing performance in any field of activity can only be achieved through a qualified and motivated human resource. The satisfaction of both students and teachers, the improvement of activities and the achievement of performances is the goal of any educational unit. We wanted to identify the problems and establish solutions and options so that, in the future, any similar situation can be managed efficiently.

Originality/value – The study takes into account a number of important factors that we considered to have had a major importance on the activities carried out. This process allowed us to perform an analysis on identifying the possibilities to fix the problems. The analysis was performed based on a questionnaire. Each questionnaire contained targeted questions, with easy-to-mark answers. In order for the answers to be authentic, the questionnaire was anonymous.

Key words: education, pandemic, teaching activity

Introduction

At the end of 2019, the crisis situation in China spread very quickly in all countries of the world. The very rapid spread of the virus has led to special measures adapted to this situation in order to protect people against this disease and also to prevent and limit the spread of the virus. [The Parliament of Romania, 2020] Studies conducted among young people show that the Covid-19 pandemic has caused both shortcomings in learning activity and an increase in the fear level, depression and anxiety caused by restrictive measures and school closure. The pandemic has had major changes in the normal way of people's lives as an effect, causing them to adapt to this crisis situation and survive. The pandemic did not affect people equally, its impact being felt differently. [The Romanian Academy, 2020,1], [The

Romanian Academy, 2020,3] This study aims to identify the main difficulties faced by students during this period and find appropriate solutions to solve these problems if such critical situations arise later.

Initial Data

Teaching and learning online has been a novelty for both teachers and students, who have had to adapt quickly and efficiently to this way of studying. [The Romanian Academy, 2020,2] Until the pandemic, technical education had no other form of teaching than face-to-face, all classes, both courses and applications, taking place at school. This was due to the specifics of the education system. Thus, changing this way of teaching in the online version was a real challenge for both teachers and students. Both the students' ability to adapt and their understanding of the notions taught were tested. At the beginning of the pandemic, the teaching was done exclusively online, then the transition was made to the hybrid system, with online courses and face-to-face applications.

The study was conducted on the basis of a questionnaire prepared in Google Forms, which was distributed to students from all years of study from the Bachelor's degree in Engineering and Construction Management at the Faculty of Civil Engineering in Cluj-Napoca. The questionnaire consisted of 12 questions, 9 of them were multiple choice and 3 were narrative questions, the latter aimed to express students' views on the topics surveyed. The questions aimed to determine how the students adapted to the online learning activities, how they managed to understand and carry out the practical activities, respectively to identify the major problems they faced during the pandemic, related to learning and socializing. The inclusion of narrative questions allowed respondents to express their views on the activities carried out and the impact that online education had on them.

Case study

The studies related to the learning activity and the way of socialization during this period, as well as the students' opinions regarding these activities are important, because using them we can form an opinion about how we managed to go through and overcome the crisis period, about the lacks and needs we had and respectively about the way of managing these newly encountered situations. The educational platform used during this period of time for the didactic activity like teaching, evaluation and, respectively, communication outside of classes was Microsoft Teams. Each teacher had to adapt his teaching method and interact with the students, depending on the specifics of the taught subject. [Ciplea, S.A, 2017]

The case study is based on the analysis of the answers received from the students. What we wanted to find out was, mainly, how the students managed to adapt to this new form of distance learning. [Mircea, A., 2019] Other main aspects viewed the social side, the access to technology and the ability of concentration and socialization.

At the beginning we considered it important to find out how the notions taught in the online version were understood, 41.8% of the respondents had the opinion that it was more difficult to understand the notions taught in this form of distance learning. This aspect may be due to the impossibility of verifying the active presence of students at the course and applications, also checking the attention to the notions taught. The way the information was received was more difficult for the teachers to manage, because the students were protected by some images on the computer screen. Also, the students' attitude and their disinterest, sometimes their absence near the computer - for a longer or shorter period of time - were factors which determined that the understanding of the concepts was not as high as expected.

Another aspect that must be analyzed is the interaction between students and teachers in the learning activity. From the answers given by the students, it follows that a 33% percentage of them got involved very little in the discussions, and 29.7% said that their involvement was the same in both methods of teaching. A percentage of 22% of those surveyed answered that it was easier for them to communicate in the online version. The reduced involvement of the students in the discussions was due to the lack of face-to-face interaction and their comfort in the online learning activity, these factors appeared and intensified with the passage of time. Because of this, the teaching staff had to make an additional effort, compared to the classroom activity, in order to maintain the students' attention during the lessons.

The fact that they were much less supervised at home than in the classroom and the disturbing external factors (characteristics of the online environment) were more numerous determined a lower interest in studying by the students, they often had a passive attitude and all this determined a decrease in the quality of education, during this period. Thus, the results show us that 53.6% of them were a little motivated to study during this period, and 11% of them were not motivated at all. The modification of the teaching method as well as the different interaction between the teacher and the student implicitly determined the modification of the students' behavior and attitude towards learning. A percentage of 31.9% of those surveyed had an attitude close to that of traditional teaching and were quite motivated to study during this period.

Analyzing the answers received to the question "What was the most important thing you missed during the pandemic regarding school activities?" we can say that the opinions were not very different. The vast majority of students felt the lack of socialization, direct interaction with colleagues and teaching staff, face-to-face communication, laboratories carried out at school, writing on the blackboard, teamwork, excursions, visits to construction sites.

Another question aimed to identify the problems and the difficult situations that the students encountered during this period. From the answers received, it follows that more than half of the students felt a distance from their colleagues and teaching staff, respectively they lacked direct contact, especially during practical activities. Other problems were those related to the lack/failure of the Internet network, respectively the lack of a suitable space for studying. Learning from home is a difficult process for some students (due to technical difficulties, space, concentration difficulties) that may appear during the semester and that may lead, at the end, to worse results than if the activities were carried out in class.

To the question "How did you perceive learning at home?" three of the four answers had a close percentage, around 30%. One of the three situations shows that the students adapted to the online environment quite well and are looking at the didactic activity as a school activity. Two of the answer options consider home learning as a combined activity between school and home activities. Learning from home can also have advantages such as mainly those related to the travel time to school, the facilities offered by technology, the possibility of attending classes from different locations. During this period, a greater presence of students was observed in the course hours, they had easier access to some information, the fast and safe distribution of some didactic materials was achieved. Also, online meetings facilitated the verification and easy explanation of certain information, such as those related to diploma projects, and information sessions were easily held outside of teaching hours.

From the answers received from the students, it can be seen that a large part of them (54.9%) did not have a problem with adapting to the new form of learning, and 38.5% adapted more difficult, but not with a great effort. Young people have the ability to adapt much more easily to changes in their lives. The online environment and technology is no longer a problem for many of them, young people having access to and using computers since pre-university education. The problem of adaptation may arise from the way everyone manages to be attentive, get involved, study and fulfill their school duties, at home not being constrained by certain factors specific to classroom activities.

The purpose of the following question "Did you feel a rupture, a detachment from school activities, during this pandemic period?" was to determine how students perceived the change in the way of learning they were used to before the pandemic. Analyzing the answers received, we can say that most of the answers were affirmative. The period of the pandemic caused a break in the activity and the students' lifestyle and caused them to go back to their home city. The period of work from home extending over a rather long period, upon the end of the restrictions and the return to school, a large part of the students needed a period of readjustment. There were students who did not feel that they made an additional effort when returning to the usual way of studying. Some of the students felt that they made an extra effort and found it difficult to return to school. The answers were different because each of the students felt and tried to accommodate themselves taking into account their character and their ability to adapt.

From the answers received to the following question, it can be seen that what was missing most during this period was socialization and direct contact with those close to them, colleagues, friends, teaching staff. The meetings were possible only with the help of the computer, on the groups made on Teams or other social networks. People had to communicate, but in a different way than the one they were used to.

Because everyone's opinion is important, at the end of the questionnaire we wanted to find out the students' personal opinions related to the pandemic, things they faced and which we did not analyze in the questionnaire.

Here are some of the students' opinions: "It was quite a difficult change to go online, which I never thought about, but personally I think we have adapted, some students better, others less"; "I think it was more difficult for the teachers. In any case, we are glad that it passed"; "It helped the development of the education system by giving students the chance to learn about such era-specific schooling"; "It had advantages and disadvantages"; "A traumatizing experience"; "The pandemic has wasted that start of energy I came with in year 1 to meet new people, to learn new things. When I started physically in year 2 I no longer had the same energy that I had at the beginning, so I consider that the pandemic stole a part of my life, which is impossible for me to ever recover"; "Besides the epidemiological risk, it was a difficult period to manage at the level of emotional balance"; "The pandemic was a time when I realized how important direct contact is for learning performance"; "It's not a period that makes us happy, but I hope we managed to face it as good as possible".

Discussion and conclusions

The pandemic has had, for the most part, a negative effect on all people, but especially the youth have suffered the most. Isolation and distancing caused the appearance of several negative effects among young people. Meetings were no longer possible, handshakes were limited, hugs were stopped. It was forbidden to organize graduation festivities, both for young people who finished high school and for students graduating from the faculty. Admission to the college was done online and the freshman ball could not be organized either. [www.mediafax.ro, 2022] They are unique events in everyone's life, which, once they have passed, cannot be rescheduled or recovered.

The pandemic made us adjust to a different way of life, work, and learning. It determined the development of new skills and a different way of spending time. The home became a school, a place to spend time, a place to meet colleagues. Online learning was a recommended solution in this crisis situation, to reduce the number of infection cases and to ensure the protection of teachers and young people. The classes could be ran well, but this proved to be more difficult than in the face-to-face teaching system. The teaching staff's management for the understanding of the concepts taught, for capturing the attention of the students as well as checking the way of working in the practical activities, was very difficult to manage during this period, due to the lack of visual contact, a feedback from the students and a suitable environment for carrying out activities.

The fast evolution of information and communication technology currently has an important influence in the development of many fields of activity as well as in the development of communication relations achieved worldwide. The changes that appeared in education during this period determined the use of the computer system as a basis for study, an important element but which must be used with caution and a lot of responsibility. In the technical field, in particular, practical work must be carried out in laboratories with the physical presence of both students and the teaching staff. Change is a constantly present element in our life. The ability to adapt to changes and become better has become a basic characteristic of all humans.

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